

Returnee Voices Matter: Towards More Inclusive Return Policies

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RETURNEE VOICES MATTER: TOWARDS MORE INCLUSIVE RETURN POLICIES

POLICY BRIEF

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Authors: Nazanine NOZARIAN (ICMPD), Madeleine HOELD (ICMPD), Sabeth KESSLER (ICMPD), Nassim MAJIDI (Samuel Hall), Juliette SAMMAN (Samuel Hall), Lisa PFISTER (Samuel Hall), Marta ROCHA (Samuel Hall), Daniel PROVOST (Samuel Hall)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This policy brief synthesises the main research findings of the FAiR working paper *Discourse and Policies: Silencing Returnees and the Need for More Inclusive Return Policies*¹ and offers actionable recommendations to enhance the inclusivity and effectiveness of return policies.

Policies are often not adapted to the needs of returnees, resulting in extreme exclusion, stigma and poverty as well as inefficiencies in terms of migration management. Not only are they not inclusive nor adapted, but policies often silence returnees, as shown in our research. Yet, if policies and practices are not improved to address these gaps, people will be pushed to migrate again as a coping mechanism, even when they are willing to reintegrate. Furthermore, the act of not being heard in return policies reduces the attractiveness of voluntary return.

The research conducted in Georgia, Iraq, Nigeria and Türkiye highlights three core arguments:

- Different types of narratives impact on the legitimacy of migration and return policies, which are typically disconnected from returnees' experiences.
- The disconnect demonstrates the frequent silencing of returnees which further nurtures their invisibilisation and dehumanisation in dominant discourses.
- Alternative discourses can contribute to more inclusive and effective return policies.

The research findings underscore that it is possible to do things differently: Discourses that emerge from countries of origin, which are not centred around European perspectives and agendas, and which are shared by returnees themselves can be the foundation for more inclusive and effective return policies.

¹ Samuel Hall, Koç University, and Erasmus University Rotterdam (2024), *Discourse and Policies: Silencing Returnees and the Need for More Inclusive Return Policies*, FAiR working paper. Available [here](#).

ABOUT THE FAiR PROJECT

The Finding Agreement in Return (FAiR) project aims to strengthen the governance of return migration in the EU, addressing the legitimacy issues around return migration policies and alternatives. The project contributes to generating new insights into the factors and processes that either foster or impede the legitimacy and effectiveness of related policies. The initiative places the perspectives of non-EU realities centre stage and brings together multidisciplinary expertise from academic, policy research, governmental, and migrant advocacy organisations across Europe, Africa, and the Middle East. This policy brief is based on qualitative data collected by the Samuel Hall research team through interviews, focus groups, validation workshops and corpus analysis in Georgia, Iraq, Nigeria and Türkiye.

INTRODUCTION

The European Union places significant emphasis on return policies within its broader migration management strategy. However, these policies often do not adequately address and integrate the human rights of returnees, resulting in inefficiencies and negative outcomes for individuals. To enhance both the effectiveness and dignity of return, policies must be reimagined to be more inclusive, taking into account the needs, preferences, and experiences of returnees themselves.

As part of the FAiR consortium, one of the research components² focuses on the legitimacy in discourses on returns, from different perspectives – states, media, civil society and returnees – and particularly from the perspective of non-European countries. Based on an analysis of how discourses in non-EU countries shape return, readmission and reintegration policies in both EU and non-EU countries, it proposes new approaches that incorporate voices and narratives from returnees (counter-discourses in this context, as they reflect perspectives from countries of origin, outside of dominant state perspectives) to ensure more inclusive return policies.

Research was led by [Samuel Hall](#) through qualitative data collection and a corpus analysis, the systematic analysis of a large body of texts to identify linguistic characteristics, patterns and insights about language use. Field research was conducted across three non-EU countries: Georgia (Tbilisi), Iraq (Duhok) and Nigeria (Abuja and Benin City). Due to challenges related to lack of access to target groups, data related to Türkiye was only collected through corpus analysis. Qualitative data collection involved a desk review, a policy mapping, key informant interviews, semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, and validation workshops. More than 350 persons have been interviewed during data collection.³

The research employed critical discourse analysis through a decolonial lens, recognising that coloniality extends beyond traditional settler colonialism. It analyses societal power dynamics by incorporating the knowledge production ecosystem (including geographical contexts and stakeholder roles) into the analysis grid. Additionally, it examined how various discourses shape self-other relations, representations and hierarchies. These elements collectively influence the opportunities available for effective policymaking.

² Work Package 4, see more details about FAiR Work Packages [here](#).

³ For more details on the research methodology see: Samuel Hall, Koç University, and Erasmus University Rotterdam (2024), *Discourse and Policies: Silencing Returnees and the Need for More Inclusive Return Policies*, FAiR working paper. Available [here](#).

KEY TAKEAWAYS FROM FAIR RESEARCH

Narratives and return policies are disconnected from returnees.

The research conducted by Samuel Hall and the corpus analysis⁴ in the four country contexts highlights a significant gap between returnees' experiences and their representation in return, readmission, and reintegration policies. These findings reveal that documents and policies either focus on the personal experiences of returnees or emphasise policy and legal discussions, but rarely connect the two. This underscores a significant disconnect between the humanisation of returnees and the policies that affect them, leaving their real-world experiences inadequately reflected.

Analysing the narratives emerging from FAiR research provides the opportunity to connect the two: the lived experiences and the policy aspects. First, by identifying narratives that come from returnees themselves, which can inform the refinement of current policies, and second, by identifying those narratives presenting opportunities for an alternative policy focus – one that would better respond to the needs and aspirations of returnees.

Across the four research countries, seven categories of dominant narratives are identified as the most relevant to return policy:

- **Assistance narratives**, which do not give much space to returnees and focus on policies, particularly on the *necessity of assistance* (with assisted voluntary return policies and references to trafficking and irregular migration overrepresented), and which do not refer to returnees' stories or quotes.
- **Legitimacy narratives**, which bring judgment to return (*forced return is not fair*), regardless of the experience or impact. While these narratives tend to include individual accounts and stories focusing on the harm associated with deportations, they only speak to forced return policies, with little reference to assistance.
- **Experience narratives**, which focus on the challenges and risks faced by returnees (*return is difficult*), are overrepresented, including via the sharing of individual stories and quotes. When these narratives mention policies, their message is critical, emphasising the hardship entailed in return.
- **Dehumanisation narratives**, which are over-represented in policy documents and are characterised by a dehumanisation of the discussion on return policies, with the complete absence of returnees' stories and a terminology focusing on numbers and legal aspects (*returnees are numbers*).

⁴ The corpus for this research was developed by selecting a diverse sample of sources that represent discourses on return, reintegration and readmission, primarily from documents published after 2010 or following readmission agreements with the EU. It includes various formats – such as policy documents, multimedia, and social interactions – ensuring comprehensive representation of different authors, perspectives and policy stances. Notably, the policy mapping reveals that only 15 out of 44 documents originate solely from governments in countries of origin, highlighting an overrepresentation of foreign agencies as policymakers and underscoring the significant influence of EU Member States and international organisations in national migration management.

- **Transnationalism narratives**, which focus on transnational relationships developed by diaspora and use a terminology associated with identity and belonging (*the nation extends to diaspora*). These narratives exclude the individual and the policy level and solely focus on the group/nation.
- **National responsibility narratives**, which hold governments in countries of origin accountable for reintegration support but also for the improvement of return policies (*the government is responsible*). These narratives focus on the political level (policy, services, development and cooperation) and rarely consider the impact of return on individuals – except in Nigeria⁵ – although they can help reconnect returnees and policymaking.
- **Impact narratives**, which connect returnees' experiences to the country of origin and its socio-economic context (*return is beneficial for the country*). This has the potential to be a bridging narrative, despite the fact that policies and assistance are underrepresented.

Most of these dominant narratives in countries of origin clearly illustrate the **disconnect between returnees and policies**. Indeed, narratives focusing on policies do not refer to returnees' experiences and perspectives. On the other hand, narratives including individual accounts and returnees' stories do not speak of policies, and when they do, they hold a predominantly negative perception towards return policies (experience narratives – *return is difficult*).

However, narratives coming from returnees themselves can have a bridging potential and create opportunities for policymakers to build more inclusive return policies.

Dominant discourses silence and dehumanise returnees.

While narratives are already indicative of the correlation between the way returnees are considered and included in public discussion and the way policies are developed and perceived, it is essential to zoom out and look at how these narratives interact with their environment to create discourses. Discourses structure social understanding and are a full part of policy-making processes and social behaviour shaping. Discourses are a form of expression, publicly accessible, through which authority relations are determined, exercised and contested. They are used to assert authority, influence others, and shape social realities. In the field of return and readmission, the power relationships are clear between states, institutions and individuals. Analysing which discourses are emphasized, ignored, or silenced is paramount to understanding how governments exercise their authority through return policies. It also reveals how these policies often fail to address or acknowledge the more harmful and uneasy aspects of return, while excluding the more harmful or uneasy aspects of return.

The FAiR research identifies eight key discourses, of which five are particularly relevant for this brief:

- **Crisis discourse**, which portrays migrants as mere statistics or criminals in Europe, neglecting the agency and positive roles of migrants, including returnees.
- **Solidarity discourse**, which highlights the experiences of returnees, advocating for increased support through broad-based assistance from civil society.

⁵ Returnees' stories and voices are largely absent from National Responsibility Narratives in Iraq and Türkiye, which highlights the disconnect between policymaking and their lived experiences. In contrast, these narratives are overrepresented in Nigeria, where documents acknowledge the collaborative efforts of federal and state governments in providing return and reintegration assistance.

- **Humanitarian discourse**, which centres on assistance, and predominates outside of the EU, where it is mainstreamed across NGO and policy discourses.
- **Development-transnational discourse**, which views diaspora and returnees as skilled individuals eager to contribute to national development, emphasising their agency and the diaspora's vision of return.
- **Government accountability discourse**, which focuses on the responsibility of governments to ensure the protection and rights of returnees as citizens, advocating for transparency, public participation and accountability in governance.

In EU countries, dominant migration discourses⁶ influence both policymaking and social behaviours based on the acceptance or rejection of migrants. However, they also influence narratives in non-EU countries: the crisis discourse and solidarity discourse in particular are also reflected in narratives in countries of origin – in turn shaping policies and behaviours in these countries.

Analysing discourses requires looking not only at the text, but also at the context of discourse production and dissemination.⁷ In other words, the messenger matters: it is not only about the content of the message but who is conveying it. For instance, in Nigeria, FAIR research highlights that the assistance narrative has a different meaning if it is carried by policymakers and NGOs or by individuals. In the first case, it corresponds to a humanitarian discourse which focuses on assistance and can dehumanise returnees; while in the second case, it is part of a solidarity discourse that recognises their voices, experiences and challenges.

An analysis of policy documents and discourses in Georgia, Iraq, Nigeria and Türkiye confirms the disconnect between returnees and policies and demonstrates a quasi-systematic silencing and dehumanisation of returnees. This dehumanisation happens by:

- **Excluding returnees from policymaking processes:** Instead, they are centred around European agendas. In the cases analysed, return policies ignore returnees, signifying that policymaking processes are influenced by discourses that reject migrants, leading to top-down processes and to the silencing of people of concern.
- **Focusing on numbers over returnees' agency:** This is illustrated by the dominance of a crisis discourse in the researched countries of origin, potentially influenced by migration discourses in the EU. This is particularly reflected in policies that focus on the intergovernmental perspective over the human experience, ultimately denying personal agency instead of working with it.

There is a correlation between the silencing of returnees, their agency in return, and cash-based support mechanisms operated by host countries in particular. Conversations held with returnees and key informants in Iraq revealed that individuals who are deported often receive less cash assistance compared to their peers who, when informed by authorities that they were not – or no longer – permitted to reside in the host country, agreed to return. This is despite the fact that individuals subjected to forced returns may receive little notice, are at a higher risk of being unprepared for reintegration, and would therefore in principle require more assistance.

⁶ Bayerl et al. (2020), *Migration to the EU. A Review of Narratives and Approaches*.

⁷ Mulderrig, J. et al., (2019), *Introducing critical policy discourse analysis*.

However, the scale of assistance provided appears to follow an almost punitive logic, whereby if the host country has been “forced” to resort to deportation, then the deportee will receive less assistance than if they are willing to cooperate. Conversely, those who choose to return of their own accord, and do so by their own means, tend to be better off, and to have clear plans following return (e.g. to open a business in their area of origin).

The degree of agency exercised in the return process, and the level of support received, present implications which find their way into public discourses surrounding returns, and the manner in which returnees are portrayed in these discourses. In short, those who receive support – and in particular those who are deported – are thought to have attracted adverse attention while in the host country, the idea being that “if you had not done anything wrong, you would not have had to leave”. Along these lines, deportees are often assumed to be criminals, drug users, or belonging to other stigmatised groups. This contributes to their being discredited and excluded in public conversations shaping the perception of returnees and the broader discourse surrounding return. On the other hand, individuals who choose to return, and who receive no assistance in doing so, are more likely to invest resources and be recognised as “positive” examples of return, whose experiences are given more weight in conversations surrounding this phenomenon, as well as in media narratives. Meanwhile, those forced returnees with the least resources, who often face the highest levels of stigma, are those whose voices are absent – even while they may serve as negative examples in everyday discourse on return and reintegration.

At the same time, access to assistance is hampered by the social exclusion faced by returnees. In Nigeria, there is a complex relationship between returnees’ will to remain anonymous, due to social stigmatisation, and the adoption of a “returnee identity” among individuals who chose to migrate to facilitate their access to assistance and, more broadly, to public services. As stated by several returnees in Nigeria, social stigma often pushes them to avoid going back to their place of origin or receiving assistance due to the fear of being judged by the community. Negative narratives and representations significantly impact returnees’ return and reintegration processes and experiences, further leading to silencing and often exclusion.

In contrast, some returnees who experienced forced return to Benin City, Nigeria, may perform a so-called “returnee identity” for donors, researchers and media channels, to enable them to access opportunities unavailable to non-returnees but also regain respect and a certain social status in the community.⁸ However, this returnee identity is also instrumentalised by European and international actors when it is used to publicly share returnees’ experiences to warn of the risks of irregular migration, with the goal of curbing it by positioning returnees as “ambassadors of regular migration”.⁹

Conversations about migration and development are characterised by the persistence of Euro-centric colonial perspectives.¹⁰ This portrayal overlooks the challenges faced by countries of origin and perpetuates the idea that social and cultural capital acquired in Europe is universally applicable.

⁸ Mariia Shaidrova (2022), *Performing a “Returnee” in Benin City, Nigeria*.

⁹ The argument of returnees as “ambassadors of regular migration” was mentioned by several key informants in Nigeria.

¹⁰ The research employed critical discourse analysis through a decolonial lens, recognising that coloniality extends beyond traditional settler colonialism. It analyses societal power dynamics by incorporating the knowledge production ecosystem (including geographical contexts and stakeholder roles) into the analysis grid. Additionally, it examined how various discourses shape self-other relations, representations and hierarchies. These elements collectively influence the opportunities available for effective policymaking.

Migrants often internalise this dominant discourse by viewing their home countries as underdeveloped.¹¹ Subsequently, while listening to returnees' experiences can help policymakers to better grasp the conditions of return, their accounts do not always reflect an “objective” reality. As previously stated, returnees' images of themselves may reflect the imagery presented in policy texts.¹²

It is essential to recentre the discussion on return policies around countries of origin, in order to better design policies and support programmes that do not silence returnees.

Bridging and alternative discourses can contribute to more inclusive and effective return policies.

Policymakers can leverage discourses that are alternative to the crisis discourse, particularly the solidarity and development-transnational discourse, to reconnect returnees, policies and policymaking processes. These two discourses, in particular, offer opportunities to humanise the conversation at several levels. First, the FAiR research indicates that these discourses are most represented among returnees themselves. Instead of ignoring or dehumanising returnees, this would help bring returnees into the conversation. Second, these discourses focus on the experience of migration (including trafficking), return (including related policies and legal frameworks), and diasporic identity. Returnees' experiences are thus made visible. Finally, these discourses present opportunities for policymaking as they focus on response: The solidarity discourse highlights the different needs of returnees, while the development-transnational discourse highlights the potential of returnees and the diaspora that can be leveraged for sustainable reintegration programmes. Thus, putting returnees and their experiences at the centre of the conversation, far from preventing efficient policy, comes with opportunities for more inclusive and sustainable policies on return that are built on the strength of returnees.

The research conducted by Samuel Hall reveals a clear gap between returnees' experiences and their reflection in policies related to return, readmission and reintegration, resulting in policies that frequently fail to capture this human perspective and a disconnect between policies and real-world experiences.

Importantly, while existing return policies are primarily aligned with discourses that silence and dehumanise returnees, the research findings also demonstrate that it is possible to do differently. Indeed, **discourses that emerge from countries of origin, which are not centred around European perspectives and agendas, and which are shared by returnees themselves, can help identify new ways forward for more inclusive and effective return policies.**

Two specific discourses emerge that offer another perspective on policies: *return is beneficial for the country* (development-transnational discourse) and *the government of the country of origin is responsible for returnees* (government accountability discourse). These discourses are key as they:

- **Focus on the perspectives of the country of origin** by looking at the concrete impact and ways to leverage return's benefits while responding to the needs and challenges of returnees. They step away from the focus on Europe to focus on what countries of origin need to fulfil their potential, with the support of returnees.

¹¹ Sinatti, G. (2013), *Return migration as a win-win-win scenario? Visions of return among Senegalese migrants, the state of origin and receiving countries.*

¹² Åkesson, L. and Baaz, M. (2015), *Africa's Return Migrants: The New Developers?*

- **Create the possibility of a common vision and collective narrative** by better including returnees' experiences and voices, reconnecting and improving information and communication lines between policies and returnees.
- **Are bridging**, meaning that they are represented across countries and contexts, types of documents (multimedia, policy, administrative, legal) and sources (alternative and mainstream). They also speak about different types of return and reintegration assistance and policies. This indicates that they can be found in multiple spaces and spheres in countries of origin, negotiating and contributing to finding agreement in return.

While policies are often not adapted to the needs of returnees, resulting in negative reintegration outcomes but also in inefficiencies in terms of migration management, they can still be improved notably through inclusive and participatory policymaking practices.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Component 1. More Inclusive Policymaking

1.1 Incorporate returnees' voices and perspectives into systems that enhance policy development, and lead to improved design of and adaptations to return and reintegration programmes. Specific actions in the short-term include:

- **Map key stakeholders and engagement pathways** to understand *who* to involve and *how* to involve migrants' participation in policymaking, initiatives and referral pathways at local, subnational and national levels;
- **Integrate regular and meaningful consultations** with returnees and other key stakeholders (such as governmental entities, municipalities, CSOs, NGOs, private sector and IOs) and establish **validation processes through feedback and complaint mechanisms**.¹³ These consultations and mechanisms could be implemented anonymously, in an online and anonymised format, as well in-person at local municipalities to ensure they lead to adaptations in policies and programmes;
- **Schedule regular feedback loops and restitution to returnees** (e.g. biannually) and proactively share information with participants concerning any adaptations or changes to the policy frameworks, support options, referral mechanisms, or any other relevant aspects of the return landscape. This will ensure that previous rounds of consultations have been used and acted upon, to build trust and ensure buy-in.
 - More regular follow-ups should reflect a broader shift in the structure of governmental and other support programmes available to returnees, building on a longer-term conceptualisation of return and reintegration as a continuum, rather than a singular event.

1.2 Direct and local funding of initiatives which integrate returnees' voices. Resources must be allocated to projects that actively engage returnees at the civil society and municipality levels. Specific actions in the medium-term include:

- **Establish and fund support groups at local level** (e.g. municipalities, CSOs) where returnees can share experiences related to their return and reintegration process (e.g. business grants application process, more general social challenges including those stemming from negative discourse) – an example of this are the exchanges organised by the European Technology Training Centre (ETTC) in Erbil, in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq;
- **Set up local centers dedicated to identifying returnees' needs, counselling them on next steps, and linking them with funding initiatives that support their reintegration**, such as the Samgori Multifunctional Center in Tbilisi, Georgia. Founded in 2024 with IOM support, it helps returnees rebuild their damaged houses by providing tools for rent (e.g. wheelbarrow, shovel), becoming a pillar of support within the community;

¹³ For further recommendations related to Monitoring, see FAiR Policy Brief: *Best Practices of Implementing a Human Rights Approach in Assisted Voluntary Return (and Reintegration)* – Introducing Human Rights Monitoring, Antonella Patteri (2024). Available [here](#).

- **Fund opportunities for the creation of returnee networks and collectives that can act as knowledge generation, advocacy platforms, and as peer-to-peer support**, reinforcing a sense of community for returnees and providing guidance and actions based on lived experiences. These networks and collectives will feed into the consultations detailed in 1.1.

Component 2. Improved Responses to the Needs of Returnees

2.1 Strengthen operational strategies and procedures at the government level to address the needs of returnees. Specific actions in the medium-term include:

- **Create a dedicated governmental unit focused specifically on return and reintegration**, as these issues are often subsumed under broader-migration related mandates, such as those focusing on emigration or refugees, and which may not provide capacity to adequately address the needs of returnees. This unit should be composed of representatives from various ministries or agencies (e.g. Ministry of the Interior, Ministry of Labour);
- **Create a national referral mechanism to support returnees** based on a comprehensive mapping of relevant actors, agencies and ministries in countries of origin. Expanding the model of the NRM operated by the Federal Government of Iraq, this mechanism should integrate non-governmental actors and service providers, and provide opportunities for meaningful participation of returnees.

2.2 Improve availability of and access to adequate support such as financial support, healthcare, education, and other essential services delivered in countries of origin by governments, municipalities, CSOs and IOs. Specific actions include both pre-return and post-return actions:

- **Conduct (pre-return) profile assessments of returnees** (e.g. age, gender, level of education, professional experience) to provide tailored assistance that addresses their exact needs and preferences, disaggregated by age (e.g. understanding the need of elderly returnees), gender (e.g. differentiating the needs of men, women and people with diverse SOGIESC), and level of education (e.g. differentiating the type of training required). These assessments should be conducted pre-return to ensure planning for reintegration activities.
- **Plan (pre-return) the integration of returnees into specific programmes** rather than categorising assistance by the “type” of return. Specifically, the practice of providing less assistance to forced returnees or to those who appealed their return decisions should be proscribed – particularly as available evidence demonstrates that this specific group may be most in need of support. Instead, the profile assessments should inform a capacity-based and needs-based approach to their integration.
- **Provide (post-return) business grants to returnees** to help them start their own businesses. Applications could be submitted online or in-person. For the in-person option, it is essential to establish a support team (e.g. at the municipal level) to assist returnees with the application processes. This is particularly important as many returnees, as seen in Georgia, may not be familiar with digital platforms.

2.3 Create evidence-based opportunities for skills development linked to the support provided in 2.2. Specific actions in the medium to long-term include:

- **Ensure skills development opportunities are aligned with returnees' needs and aspirations** through participatory monitoring and consultation processes, and ensure vocational training programmes are aligned with existing skills and local needs through **participatory market assessments** involving local authorities, returnees and private sector employers.
- **Establish platforms fostering regular exchanges between private sector employers, government authorities, non-governmental reintegration practitioners, and returnees.** Such spaces as they currently exist [as seen in Iraq through the Multi Stakeholder Platform (MSP) involving the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, and various Chambers of Commerce] can serve as a model to be expanded upon with greater attention to the inclusion of returnees in high-level meetings and conversations.

2.4 Improve access to and monitoring of governmental support made available to returnees. Specific actions in the short-term include:

- **Engage municipalities and civil society organisations in return and reintegration programmes** due to their local footprint and proximity to citizens, and require regular monitoring updates on the progress of these programmes;
- **Establish a centralised online platform and physical information centers** such as those at MRCs or municipal levels to ensure returnees, including those with limited internet literacy, can access information on available support programmes, respective application processes, and eligibility criteria.

Component 3. Enhanced Information and Communication to Connect Returnees and Policies

3.1 Promote a mindset shift by challenging biases against migrants' knowledge and building an approach that actively supports and values migrants' participation in policymaking processes. Specific actions in the medium-term include:

- **Develop targeted information and communication strategies** for existing return and reintegration support by engaging governments, diplomatic representations, and media. Specific actions in the medium-term include:
 - **Design comprehensive communication campaigns** to ensure returnees receive timely, accurate and comprehensive information about the reintegration support available, their rights, and their entitlements;
 - **Develop multi-platform awareness-raising campaigns** that engage media outlets, religious actors, local leaders, communities, and returnees in order to identify and include counter-discourses or alternative viewpoints that challenge stereotypes about return and reintegration. These campaigns should aim to move away from negative discourses such as the 'crisis discourse' and involve a whole-of-society approach;

- **Include host communities in areas of high return in awareness raising campaigns seeking to reduce stigma and combat negative discourse surrounding return.**
 - Facilitate “town hall” type meetings to discuss the challenges faced by returnees, shed light on certain misconstrued notions surrounding life in Europe and the decision to return, and illustrate the added value of returnees to the communities to which they return;
 - Through these participatory initiatives, make inclusivity a standard practice and operational principle to ensure policies are relevant, effective and address the real needs of returnees, while avoiding any impression of preferential treatment which might disrupt social cohesion and undermine reintegration.

The list of actors may differ depending on the country. For example, in Georgia, religious actors have a significant influence on how returnees are perceived by the community; in Iraq, social media influencers, businesspeople, and local authorities were key figures in shaping the perception of returnees.

3.2 Establish effective communication channels between policymakers and returnees, in order to facilitate continuous dialogue to bridge the gap between policy and practice, ensuring returnees’ needs and experiences feed into policy development. Specific actions in the medium-term include:

- **Embed Migrant Resource Centres within Governmental line ministries**, as is the case notably with the ICMPD MRC embedded in MoLSA in Baghdad, Iraq.

In conclusion, to develop sustainable and legitimate solutions for return, readmission and reintegration, it is essential to **move beyond EU-centred perceptions that distance policymakers from the realities of returnees**. Instead, policies should focus on the individuals and contexts to which returnees return. Implementing such participatory policymaking processes is crucial to ensure that the needs and perspectives of returnees are genuinely addressed.